

4D PRINTING OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

3D printing serves as an essential tool towards fabricating customized implants catering to individual needs. Where implant materials must conform to stringent compatibility norms, adding a different material for each function entails cumbersome and expensive testing, and at the same time increase the risk and discomfort to the user. For example, it is ideal to have a human stent, that is - i) small enough to pass through the blood vessels before it reaches the desired location, ii) expandable at its final location, iii) strong enough to avoid closure of the arteries, iv) able to sense the closure of the arteries during its service, v) self-repairable to avoid repetitive surgeries, vi) conforming to the dimensions of each patient. As of now, a single stent cannot cater to all these functions. In our work, we resolve four of the six above-mentioned constraints. We have designed a new material which exhibits shape memory and piezoelectric behaviour and is 3D printable. We developed and 3D printed a nanocomposite of PLA with piezoelectric barium titanate to create actuators that can feel. We foresee a broad range of applications in the field of robotics and biomedicine for our multifunctional materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

An important quality that distinguishes natural structures from the synthetic ones is the ability to sense, process, and respond to stimuli at the same time [1]. In a product, usually various components are used to serve different functions like varying mechanical properties: strength, stiffness, and toughness; with additional features like actuation, sensing, electrical or thermal connections, damping, and protection from environmental conditions. Like the natural systems where two or more properties are combined within a single component, the idea of this project is to develop materials possessing more than one function and then further tune the architecture of the printed structures to achieve additional properties. In this regard, 3D printing comes in as a valuable tool that creates multifunctional adaptive structures on a single platform along with the advantages of customizing a product towards individual needs. 4D printing further involves creating objects via 3D printing that change their shape with time [2, 3].

Large elastic deformation in shape memory polymers (SMPs) presents their case for soft robotics. Sensors integrated within these actuators would provide a feedback of the latter's function as well as health, and ensure their efficient functioning over the course of their lifetime especially when actuating elements are inaccessible for repair. One such example, is a vascular stent, used for supporting blood vessels. The advantages of a stent made from a shape memory polymer is that, it could be compacted temporarily during its transport and expanded to its initial size when the stent reaches its final destination [4]. The abilities of the implanted stents to further detect anomalies in the blood pressure are being increasingly investigated via incorporating pressure sensors along with the stents [5, 6].

Several 3D printing approaches have been defined towards the fabrication of SMP structures including fused deposition modelling (FDM) [7], stereo-lithography [8], Polyjet [9], and direct-write (DW) [10]. DW further provides the flexibility to alter the materials composition to achieve the desired properties. It further allows for possible automation of the fabrication process, making it efficient and scalable. Piezoelectric fillers added to SMPs, as sensors in the actuated structure, aid in its structural health monitoring [11, 12].

In our work, we first chose polyurethane (PU) for the shape memory behaviour. But after the preliminary tests, it was found that the PU had a very low glass transition temperature for the desired

application, and hence, it was abandoned. Polylactic acid (PLA) was then chosen as the base material due to its shape memory properties [13, 14] for the actuator. PLA has also been a material widely researched for polymeric stents [4]. The sensing behaviour was attained by incorporating barium titanate (BTN) nanoparticles as piezoelectric fillers [15].

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

A material system for 3D printing with varying degrees of piezoelectric and shape memory properties is developed and characterized.

2.1 Materials

A two-part polyurethane (PU, Polyol, RAMPF[®]) was earlier chosen as the matrix material and then replaced by polylactic acid (PLA, Ingeo[™] Biopolymer 4043D, Natureworks). Barium titanate (BTN, 100 nm, Get nano materials – OOCAP INC) was used as the piezoelectric filler.

2.2 Ink preparation

PU was mixed with the hardener in a ratio of 100:17. 10 and 20 wt.% of BTN were added to polyurethane (PU) via manual stirring. Additionally, 9 and 17 wt.% short carbon fibers were also added to an additional batch of the abovementioned mixtures.

In a different set, 2 g of PLA was added to 8 g of dichloromethane (DCM, Chemie Brunschwig AG) and let to rest for 24 h (until complete dissolution of the PLA). DCM was chosen for its high evaporation rate. 10 wt.% BTN was added to the mixture of PLA and DCM via mechanical stirring. Silver print conductive liquid paint (842 WB, MG Chemicals; 0.2 Ohm x mil resistivity) was used to form electrodes for the piezoelectric tests.

2.3 Printing

The inks prepared by the combination of different quantities of the fillers were 3D printed using the DW technique. In this technique, the material in its fluid state is filled into a syringe barrel that is mounted on a robotic arm (TR83400-06, H. Sigrist & Partner AG) with two translational degrees of freedom [16]. The additional third degree of freedom is provided by the moving stage on which the structures are printed. The material is extruded from the barrel via pneumatic pressure (D3PDSA-02 - Analoges Dosiergerät, H. Sigrist & Partner AG). The gel time of the PU system was about a few minutes depending on the concentration of the fillers. This allowed enough time to print the PU based films which were then let to cure completely for 24 h. In case of the PLA system, as the ink exited the nozzle, the solvents evaporated and the material solidified and retained the programmed structure. All the films were printed with a 250 μm nozzle, at 1 kPa extrusion pressure and the stage velocity of 15 mm s^{-1} .

2.4 Characterization

For the preliminary tests, to determine the actuation time flat PU based films were heated to 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and curled up along the longer edge to fixate them into the rolled up shape. They were then cooled down in the restrained state to room temperature. The curled films were then immersed into a hot water bath at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, their actuation times were recorded.

Glass transition temperature (T_g) of PLA (both as purchased and 3D printed) was measured with a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, Mettler Toledo) between -60 and 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. The shape memory behavior and the effect of the fillers on the piezoelectric properties of the printed PLA structures ($1.5 \times 1.5 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$) were evaluated with a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA, DMA7e, Perkin Elmer) in 3-point bending mode. These printed structures were 5 layers thick. The shape memory properties were measured for 4 cycles each involving heating, deforming, fixation, and recovery. In each cycle, the specimen was heated to 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, it was then deformed with a given force and cooled to room temperature to fix the shape. To recover the shape, the specimen was heated again to 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Forces of 1, 2, and 6 N were applied to measure the extent of possible recoverable deformation. Two specimen were tested twice each to confirm the behavior. The piezoelectric

properties were studied in the compression mode by applying a dynamic compressive force of 0.5 N at a frequency of 1 Hz for 60 cycles at room temperature.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Preliminary tests with PU

PU mixtures were cast into rectangular films (4 cm × 2 cm). Fig. 1 (a-c) shows optical microscopic images of the PU-based films with and without the fillers. Considerable amount of BTN agglomerations are visible in the nanocomposites. Improved mixing methods beyond manual stirring will help achieve a uniform distribution of the fillers and create a homogenous ink for printing. Short carbon fibers (CF) were added to PU and the other two mixtures to increase the heat transfer within the material and thus, the actuation times. Fig. 2(d) shows a micrograph of a printed PU film reinforced with CF. All the CF are well-oriented in the print direction. The capability to control the directional arrangement of the CF helps in programming the actuation directions as well as achieving local stiffening of the printed structure.

Figure 1: Optical microscopic images: (a) PU; (b) PU + 10 wt.% BTN; and (c) PU + 20 wt.% BTN; (d) PU + 9 wt.% CF.

Fig. 2(a) shows a PU film as cast, whereas the Fig. 2(b) shows the deformed state of the film. For the actuation tests, the deformed films were dropped into hot water bath at 95 °C. The time to recover the film shape is presented in Table 1.

Figure 2: (a) Initial shape of the PU film; (b) restrained shape of the PU film.

As seen from Table. 1, the actuation times of all the mixtures increased considerably with the addition of the CF. It should also be noted that the CF addition also increased the stiffness of the composites, which further increases the actuation forces (not measured in this case).

Sample Number	BTN (wt.%)	Short CF (wt.%)	Actuation time (s)
1	0	0	3
2	10	0	6
3	20	0	8
4	0	9	0.5
5	0	17	0.5
7	10	9	0.5
8	10	17	1
9	20	9	2
10	20	17	Did not actuate

Table 1: Actuation times of all the PU based films (Nomenclature: all the films have PU as the matrix, the second and the third column display the amount of the particular filler added).

The PU films without CF reinforcement did not possess the desired strength and stiffness for our stent application and hence, we shifted to a PLA based material system. Also, the longer cure times of the PU based composites inhibited their printing in the z-direction (out-of-plane).

3.2 Glass Transition temperature of PLA

The glass transition temperature (T_g) is the temperature above which the stiffness of a material decreases drastically. When heated above the T_g the polymer softens allowing for the shape change. Fig. 3, shows heating curves for both as purchased and the 3D printed PLA. The lower T_g of the 3D printed PLA can be attributed to the increased porosity due to the solution based printing technique.

Figure 3: Glass transition temperatures of PLA obtained from DSC.

3.3 Shape memory behavior

Figure 4: Shape memory curve of a PLA sample with a deforming compressive load of 6 N.

Fig. 4 represents a typical test process used to study the shape memory behaviour of the printed PLA structures comprising of four cycles of heating, programming followed by recovery. The first point on the curve is the start at room temperature and zero strain. The second point represents the strain in the material after it was heated to 80 °C and deformed with a load of 6 N. The pictures

pertaining to the points in blue on the curve show the locked deformed shape, after cooling down to the room temperature. Finally, the pictures bordered red correspond to the red points on the curve, where the recovered material was reheated to 80 °C.

The recovery strain is calculated by the following equation [17]:

$$R = (1 - (\varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_{i-1}) / (100 - \varepsilon_{i-1})) * 100 \% \quad (1)$$

where ε_i and ε_{i-1} are the strain at the beginning of the i^{th} and the end of the $i-1^{\text{th}}$ cycle, respectively. From equation 1, the values of the recovery strain for the PLA were ~91 % for all the loadings: 1, 2 (curves not shown here) and 6 N.

3.4 Piezoelectric tests

The PLA/BTN films produced an average peak-to-peak voltage of about of 4V. Fig. 5 shows a sample curve of a part of the output voltage from the PLA film with 10 wt.% BTN when loaded dynamically in the DMA.

Figure 5: Piezoelectric voltage output from the PLA/BTN film with a dynamic load of 0.5 N at a frequency of 1 Hz.

3.5 3D printed stent

Figure 6: Folding and recovery of the final 3D printed PLA/BTN stent.

Fig. 6 shows a 3D printed film rolled in the form of a cylinder (a). The cylinder was then heated over 80 °C and folded to the second shape (Fig. 6(b)) in order to attain a smaller diameter. The final structure (Fig. 6(c)) was then actuated by dipping the folded structure into a hot water bath.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Our work proved the possibility to attain multiple functions into a single structure printed from a single nanocomposite. 3D printability of this multifunctional nanocomposite opens up applications in biomedical implants and robotics. However, the recovery strains need to be improved considerably via addition of other polymers as soft segments to PLA to improve the shape memory behavior. The piezoelectric properties could also be improved by in situ poling of the fabricated nanocomposite. As addition of short fibers increases the actuation force and stiffness of the structures, a varying distribution of the fillers could be used to actuate different regions within the structure at different rates. Further effective methods of mixing the materials should be investigated to improve the filler distribution as well as printability of the nanocomposite solutions.

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